

consistent with the Witelson hypothesis that left-handedness is a consequence of disturbances in the naturally occurring loss of axons during prenatal brain shaping period. We suggest that atypically wired brains might provide a biological base for atypical problem solving abilities and artistic skills.

EEG-ABNORMALITIES LATERALIZATION TO THE LEFT HEMISPHERE FOLLOWING OBJECT "SHELTER" TRANSFORMATION TO ECOLOGICALLY SAFE SYSTEM

K. Loganovsky, I. Perchuk

Research Center for Radiation Medicine, Academy of Medical Sciences, Kiev, Ukraine

Quantitative electroencephalogram (qEEG) is a new perspective tool for biotetection and biodosimetry of ionizing radiation (Loganovsky and Yuryev, 2004). The unique radiological risks of the works on the object "Shelter" transformation to ecologically safe system include potential internal exposure to transuranium elements (238Pu, 239Pu, 240Pu, 241Pu, 241Am) as well as 90Sr and 137 Cs together with external exposure that are modified by non-radiation industrial hazards. Recently, it becomes clear that the brain is a target organ, as are the kidneys, after exposure to uranium (Lestaevel P. et al., 2005). At the baseline (before an entrance in the object "Shelter") and after plutonium incorporation the personnel (n=166) mobilized to carry out the works for the object "Shelter" transformation to ecologically safe system were examined by qEEG. Their total doses of exposure were under the dose limit of 20 mSv per year (I. Likhtarev, S. Nechaev, 2005). Following the work at the Shelter the EEG-abnormalities in comparison with the baseline level were revealed as follows: increasing of integral EEG-abnormalities ($t=7.3$; $p<0.001$); slow brain electrical activity increasing ($t=6.4$; $p<0.001$); absolute and relative β -power of qEEG increasing at the left temporal area ($t=4.4$; $p<0.002$). These neurophysiological findings testify to overactivation of cortical-limbic system predominantly in the dominant, left hemisphere. This EEG-pattern is the cerebral basis of the Chronic Fatigue Syndrome following exposure to low and very low doses of ionizing radiation, neurotoxicity of transuranium element, stress and other non-radiation industrial hazards.

NEUROPSYCHIATRIC DISORDERS IN PERSONNEL WORKING ON OBJECT "SHELTER" TRANSFORMATION TO ECOLOGICALLY SAFE SYSTEM

K.N. Loganovsky, M.A. Bomko, N.Yu. Chuprovskaja, Ye.Yu. Antipchuk, I.V. Perchuk, T.K. Loganovskaja, N.V. Deniysuk, L.L. Zdorenko, V.I. Kravchenko, N.V. Drozdova, Z.L. Vasilenko, Ye. N. Yukhimenko, S.A. Chumak, E.A. Kolosinskaja, G.Yu. Kreinis

Research Center for Radiation Medicine, Academy of Medical Sciences, Kiev, Ukraine

The personnel (n=192) mobilized to carry out the works for the object "Shelter" transformation to ecologically safe system have passed the neuropsychiatric assessment at the baseline (before the entrance in the object "Shelter") and after plutonium incorporation. Their total doses of exposure were under the dose limit of 20 mSv per year (I. Likhtarev, S. Nechaev, 2005). At baseline 62 persons (32.3%) from the personnel with mild mental and behavioral disorders were allowed to work at the "Shelter". However, following the works, such disorders were present in 81 persons (42.2%) from the personnel ($\chi^2=4.02$; $p<0.05$). The psychopathologies mainly included: organic asthenic disorder, mild cognitive impairment, neurasthenia, somatoform dysfunction, and deviations on EEG. Mild neurological disorders were diagnosed in 102 of persons (53.1%) during the input medical control and in 119 (62%) following the works ($\chi^2=3.08$; $p>0.05$). Chronic cerebrovascular and autonomic nervous system pathology were predominant. Neurasthenia, somatoform dysfunction, autonomic nervous system abnormalities and EEG-changes may be considered at the frame of Chronic Fatigue Syndrome (CFS). Among the main risk factors for CFS development should be assessed psychological stress, exposure to low and very low doses of ionizing radiation, as well as neurotoxicity of transuranium elements. Neuroprotection for CFS and related states should be developed including psychotherapy, psychoprophylaxis, psychorehabilitation and cognitive enhancers.

IMPORTANCE OF EMOTIONAL ADAPTATION OF PATIENT WITH LOW BACK PAIN TREATED WITH MELOXICAM (MOVALIS®)

Nataša Milenović, Budimir Popović

Institute for Rheumatology, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Futoška 68, Novi Sad, Serbia and Montenegro

Low back pain (LBP), one of the most common disease modern human, with huge cure and rehabilitation expenses, long-term continual medical treatment, caused that it began huge medical, psycho-social and economical problem. Aim of the study was to evaluate influences of emotional adaptability on patient self-evaluation state of health (SH) after meloxicam (Movalis®) injection and tablet in therapy of LBP. We examined 48 patients (20 male and 28 female), age 45–75, dissatisfied with other NSAID. Patients were given at the beginning three 15 mg injection of Movalis® once-daily and continued with two weeks 7,5 mg tablet once-daily. We used patient scale of self-evaluation SH, adverse event (AE) and therapeutic effect (TE). Local bearability at the site of injection one hour after injection was described by patient in 63.2% as very well after first injection and after last in 68.4%, but differences was not statistically significant ($p=0.067$) with trend to stay stable during hole period of application. Patients did not emphasize importance AE with conducted to better SH and in 47.4% of patient described their SH as satisfied after injection, although at the beginning in 94.7% described as unsatisfied. At the end 47.2% patients described SH as good. Significant improvement ($p=0.002$) was after transfer from injection to seven-day tablet treatment. Patient self-evaluation of disease and SH did not shown statistically significant gender difference. When patient had to compare Movalis® with other NSAID better efficiency was shown in 36.8% and better bearability in 94.7% patients. Good emotional adaptation and reduction AE led to good self-evaluation SH which application Movalis® injections and tablet shown as safety and good choice in therapy of LBP.

LATENT VS. MANIFEST SOCIAL NETWORKS: A PSYCHOPHYSIOLOGICAL AND SOCIOMETRIC EMPIRICAL INVESTIGATION

David I. Opris¹, Alina S. Rusu¹, Marius I. Benta²

¹ Psychology Department, Babes-Bolyai University, Cluj, Romania

² Sociology Department, University College Cork, Ireland

Little research has been done so far on latent social networks and their development into manifest networks. Latent social networks are generally defined as structures that cannot normally be observed directly. Yet, modern psychophysiological investigation techniques can provide indirect indicators of such latent networks. In this study, we have combined psychophysiological measurements with a sociometric test to study a set of 40 young individuals (20–30 year old students, of which 20 males and 20 females unknown to each other) who were involved in both a latent and a manifest network. Prior to the experiment, the subjects filled in a questionnaire comprising self-assessment items and a description of their ideal mates. Each subject was exposed to the series of 40 photographs of all the others, including themselves. Psychophysiological (electrodermal, cardiovascular and electromyographic measurements performed with a BioPAC MP 150) as well as sociometric data were collected during exposure time. This phase was replicated on the same set of persons after they were exposed to all the information gathered in the first-phase questionnaire. Data were analysed using statistics and social network analysis software (SPSS, Agna, and UCINET). Our results indicate an overlapping of the two types of preference clustering of the individuals: sociometrical and psychophysiological. Moreover, it appears that the informational framing of the members of a latent network can alter the configuration of that network's manifest crystallisation.

REM-REBOUND PHENOMENON FOLLOWING NCPAP APPLICATION IN PATIENTS WITH OSA

Bozhidar Dimitrov¹, Slavcho Slavchev²

¹Institute of Psychology, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences and ²MANA Medical Centre, Sofia, Bulgaria

The Syndrome of Obstructive Sleep Apnea (OSA), among many deteriorative symptoms it comprises, is notoriously linked with total disruption of the normal